

DAMPING FROM THERMOELASTICITY IN STRUCTURES UNDER TORSIONAL LOADING

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Abstract. *The study of damping is a fundamental area in mechanical vibrations. Damping is the cause of the loss of energy in vibrating structures. However, the process in which the energy is dissipated depends on the material properties, structure, and other parameters. One of the base sources of damping in solid materials is the conversion of energy into heat, which can be modeled using the thermoelastic model. This model couples the standard mechanical wave equation with the heat equation and predicts that the dissipated energy is converted into Entropy. While thermoelastic damping is more prominent in smaller structures (e.g., microresonators), it is present in all structures under any deformation that generates a change in volume, albeit at the lower end of the frequency spectrum. The main goal of this paper is to determine the damping profile with the frequency generated by the torsional load in non-circular cross-section structures using a Finite Element Analysis with 3D solid elements. The simulation results show that, while the thermoelastic damping generated by torsion is smaller than the one generated by bending, it cannot be ignored for some noncircular cross-sectioned geometries.*

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermoelastic damping is an intrinsic phenomenon in all structures and is a fundamental source of structural energy dissipation [5, 4]. The thermoelastic model originates from first principles, coupling the elastic wave equation with the heat conduction equation. Although its theoretical foundation was established in the 1950s [1, 3], the complexity of the model required the advent of modern computational methods for in-depth analysis [19, 2, 21, 13, 3, 4].

Damping arises from irreversible entropy generation caused by deformation-induced internal heat fluxes. This energy dissipation mechanism is especially significant in both very small and very large structures operating at low frequencies [4, 11, 9, 8]. At the microscale, temperature effects substantially influence vibration behavior and must be carefully considered [22, 23, 24, 15]. As such, a thorough understanding of thermoelastic damping is essential for designing optimized mechanical systems.

Depending on the application, damping can be either detrimental or beneficial. For instance, in microresonators, excessive damping may degrade performance [22, 23, 20], whereas in microscale damping devices, it plays a crucial functional role [12, 7, 10, 15, 20]. While there are some previous works regarding the effect of torsion in thermoelasticity, most use simplified 1D models or focus only on the thermal side of the problem, [15, 24, 18]. The main goal of this work is to study the behavior of damping generated by the thermoelastic model in geometries under torsional loads. A 3D quadratic solid Finite Element Analysis is used to give more accurate results. Solid elements are computationally more demanding due to the requirement for finer meshes to accurately capture bending and torsional phenomena. However, they offer greater versatility and insight into local phenomena, such as detailed temperature variation across the thickness [4].

This article is structured into four sections: Introduction, Materials and Methods, Results and Discussion, and Conclusions. The Materials and Methods section elaborates on the formulation of the thermoelastic model and the 3D quadratic hexahedral solid elements. The Results and Discussion section covers the mesh generation process, convergence studies, and simulation results. The Conclusions section provides a summary of the study findings.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 The Thermoelastic Model

The thermoelastic model or linear thermoelasticity dynamic model results from the complete coupling of the elastic wave equation with the heat equation and is given by (1):

$$\begin{cases} \rho \ddot{\mathbf{u}} - \mu \nabla^2 \mathbf{u} - (\lambda + \mu) \nabla (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}) + \gamma \nabla \theta = f \\ \rho C_p \dot{\theta} - k \nabla^2 \theta + \gamma T_0 (\nabla \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}}) = q, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{u} is the displacement vector ($\mathbf{u} = [u_x, u_y, u_z]^T$), θ is the temperature variation, f is the body load and q is the body heat flux. All function quantities are functions of the Euclidean coordinates and time. The constants in the model are the material properties: density (ρ), Lamé constants (μ and λ), specific heat capacity (C_p), and thermal conductivity (k).

The Lamé constants are given by:

$$\lambda = \frac{\nu E}{(1 + \nu)(1 - 2\nu)}, \quad (2a)$$

$$\mu = \frac{E}{2(1 + \nu)}, \quad (2b)$$

where E is the Young modulus and ν is the Poisson coefficient.

Since temperature is critical to the problem, all coefficients must be specified at the same base temperature T_0 , the point around which linearization is performed in the thermoelastic model. Finally, the coefficient γ is the coupling term and is given by:

$$\gamma = (3\lambda + 2\mu)\alpha, \quad (3)$$

where α is the linear thermal expansion coefficient since equation (1) is a linearized equation, it is only valid for small deformations and small temperature variations: $\frac{\theta}{T_0} \ll 1$.

2.2 Energy flow and balance in the thermoelastic model

Because it couples two fields in a single system, the thermoelastic model has some particularities regarding energy flow, especially when compared with the standard elastic wave equation. Analyzing the energy flow makes it possible to understand the phenomena behind the damping predicted by this model. A complete representation of the energy flow in the system can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Energy flow in the thermoelastic model. The wave equation originates energies marked in blue, and energies marked in orange are originated by the heat equation, [4].

The only non-conservative energy in the domain is the work lost to irreversible Entropy generation. One of the characteristics of the equation (1) is that the damping term is not explicit, much unlike all other damping models used in mechanical vibrations. Damping

occurs by generating irreversible Entropy due to the existing internal heat fluxes. The irreversible entropy is generated whenever there is a heat flux in the material, and the total energy lost this way is given by the Gouy-Stodola theorem, [19]:

$$W_S = \frac{k}{T_0} \iint_{\Omega} \nabla\theta \cdot \nabla\theta \, dV \, dt, \quad (4)$$

where W_S is the work lost to irreversible entropy.

In light of the First Law of Thermodynamics, the complete energy balance is given by the following equation:

$$\Delta U = \mathcal{V} + \mathcal{T} + \mathcal{B} + W_S = W - Q, \quad (5)$$

where ΔU is the variation of the internal energy, \mathcal{V} is the mechanical potential energy, \mathcal{T} is the kinetic energy and \mathcal{B} is the Exergy of the system. W and Q are the work and heat flows in the system (through the boundaries or in form of volumetric sources).

Since this study is focused on harmonic analysis, all conservative energies in a cycle are zero, and all boundaries will be considered Adiabatic ($Q = 0$), the Equation 5 reduces to:

$$\Delta U_{\text{cycle}} = W_{S_{\text{cycle}}} = W_{\text{cycle}}, \quad (6)$$

From Equation 6, the dissipated energy can be determined either by computing the work done to the system or by determining the energy lost to entropy (Equation 4). However, neither measure is a suitable quantifier for the system damping since it is susceptible to resonance. As such, they are not generic or comparable enough. An alternative is to use the loss angle or an equivalent damping factor.

The loss angle is a quantity widely used in material science to characterize damping in viscoelastic materials and is the phase of a complex Young modulus definition:

$$E^* = E' + E''i = E(1 + \tan(\phi_E)i) \quad (7)$$

where E^* is the dynamic modulus, E' is the storage modulus (reduces to the Young Modulus in purely elastic materials), E'' is the loss modulus that quantifies the dissipated elastic energy, and ϕ_E is the loss angle.

The loss angle is related to the hysteretic model and the hysteretic damping coefficient:

$$\phi_E = \arctan \eta \quad (8)$$

where η is the hysteretic damping coefficient.

For the hysteretic model, the damping coefficient can be extracted from Equation 4 using:

$$\eta(\omega) = \frac{W_{S_{\text{cycle}}}}{\pi k \Re(X)^2}, \quad (9)$$

where k is the stiffness of the spring, and X is the complex amplitude of the displacement. The denominator of Equation 9 is the maximum potential energy in a cycle. The equivalent hysteretic damping coefficient is also known in the literature as the quality factor $(Q_{TED}^{-1})^1$, [25, 14, 17].

2.3 Finite Element model

The thermoelastic model was implemented on an in-house Finite Element Analysis software in 2D quadrilateral and 3D hexahedral solid elements (linear and quadratic), [4]. The software was written in C++ and Intel[®] Math Kernel Library performs the linear algebra routines.

For this study, a solid standard 27 nodes quadratic hexahedral 3D element was defined according to the Figure 2.

Figure 2: Twenty seven node 3D quadratic solid element.

The full discretized version of Equation 1 is given by Equation 10

$$\mathcal{M} \begin{bmatrix} \ddot{u}_x \\ \ddot{u}_y \\ \ddot{u}_z \\ \ddot{\theta} \end{bmatrix} + \mathcal{C} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{u}_x \\ \dot{u}_y \\ \dot{u}_z \\ \dot{\theta} \end{bmatrix} + \mathcal{K} \begin{bmatrix} u_x \\ u_y \\ u_z \\ \theta \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M}f_x \\ \mathbf{M}f_y \\ \mathbf{M}f_z \\ \mathbf{M}q \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

where u_x , u_y and u_z are the displacements in the x , y and z directions, respectively, \mathcal{M} , \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{K} , are the mass, velocity² and stiffness matrices. For more details on the matrices, please refer to [4].

¹The TED under script refers to the thermoelastic damping. The quality factor can be defined as any damping.

²The term damping matrix should be avoided because the damping in the thermoelastic model is not completely contained in this matrix.

2.4 Harmonic solution

To get the solution of the harmonic problem, a Fourier transform must be applied to Equation 10:

$$(-\mathbf{M}\omega^2 + \mathbf{C}\omega i + (\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}_\Theta)) \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{U}_x \\ \mathbf{U}_y \\ \mathbf{U}_z \\ \Theta \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M}\mathbf{F}_x \\ \mathbf{M}\mathbf{F}_y \\ \mathbf{M}\mathbf{F}_z \\ \mathbf{M}\mathbf{Q} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \sum_i^{N_b} \mathbf{m}_i \mathbf{P}_x \\ \sum_i^{N_b} \mathbf{m}_i \mathbf{P}_y \\ \sum_i^{N_b} \mathbf{m}_i \mathbf{P}_z \\ \sum_i^{N_b} \mathbf{m}_i \mathbf{Q}_b \end{bmatrix}, \quad (11)$$

where ω is the angular frequency of the excitation and \mathbf{U} , Θ , \mathbf{F} , \mathbf{Q} , \mathbf{P} and \mathbf{Q}_b are the complex amplitudes of the displacements, temperature variation, body forces, body heat fluxes, boundary loads and boundary heat fluxes, respectively. The matrices \mathbf{m} are the boundary integration matrices. The matrix \mathbf{K}_Θ contains the Robin BC elements of the thermoelastic BCs, where \mathbf{m}_{ni_x} are the boundary integration matrices weighted by the normal vector, [4]

$$\mathbf{K}_\Theta = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & \sum_i^{N_b} \gamma \mathbf{m}_{ni_x} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \sum_i^{N_b} \gamma \mathbf{m}_{ni_y} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \sum_i^{N_b} \gamma \mathbf{m}_{ni_z} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (12)$$

Finally, to apply Dirichlet BCs, the system matrix must be decoupled accordingly. To obtain the complex amplitudes (and the corresponding amplitudes and phases), Equation 11 is solved using the linear equation solver.

2.5 Energy computation in the finite element model

For a harmonic analysis, as stated by Equation 6, only the boundary energy fluxes and the work lost to irreversible Entropy need to be determined. To determine these quantities used the finite element model, Equation 4 must be discretized and integrated for a complete cycle ($0 \leq t < \frac{2\pi}{\omega}$). The discretized Gouy-Stodola theorem for a cycle is given by:

$$W_{S_{\text{cycle}}} = \frac{\pi}{T_0 \omega} (\Re(\Theta)^T \mathbf{K}_\theta \Re(\Theta) + \Im(\Theta)^T \mathbf{K}_\theta \Im(\Theta)), \quad (13)$$

where \mathbf{K}_θ is the stiffness matrix for the thermal part of the model, [4]. The equivalent hysteretic damping coefficient is determined by:

$$\eta(\omega) = \frac{W_{S_{\text{cycle}}}}{\pi \begin{bmatrix} \Re(\mathbf{U}) \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}^T \mathbf{K} \begin{bmatrix} \Re(\mathbf{U}) \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}} \quad (14)$$

2.6 Geometries and materials

This work used four geometries: a circular-section beam, a square-section beam, a square plate, and a symmetrical ASTM A6 wide flange I-beam (W150x100x24). The length of

all beams in this study is 3.2m, guaranteeing a length/height ratio of 20 (meaning the maximum thickness of the beams is 0.16m). The square plate has dimensions of 3.2m by 3.2m by 0.16m.

All geometries are made of Copper, with the material properties shown in Table 1.

Property	Unit	Copper
Young modulus	GPa	120
Poisson coefficient	-	0.355
Density	kg/m ³	8960
Thermal expansion coefficient	K ⁻¹	16.7×10^{-6}
Conductivity	W/(m · K)	401
Specific heat capacity	J/(kg · K)	385

Table 1: Properties of the materials used in this study. All properties are taken at a base temperature, T_0 , of 293.15K.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Validation Study

The software and models used in this study were validated against other models and works. Full details on the validation studies can be consulted in [16] and [4].

A mesh converge study was done for every geometry using the maximum displacement as the convergence criterion. The primary variable for the convergence was the number of length-wise elements (N_L). The number of elements in the other direction was set according to the length-wise element. For the I-beam, the equations that define the mesh are in [4]. The mesh convergence studies for bending can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Mesh convergence studies for bending for: (a) circular beam, (b) square beam, (c) plate, (d) I-beam.

For torsion, it was verified that the convergence followed a similar pattern as bending. Also, for the circular beam, in torsion, quadratic elements give the exact solution; as such, fewer elements are needed. The final meshes can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Meshes for: (a) circular beam, (b) square beam, (c) plate, (d) I-beam.

3.2 Case studies

In this study, the deformation and temperature variation of the four geometries were simulated for a clamped-free configuration (along the length in the x-axis), and an external load was applied at $x = L$. For bending cases, the load is constant along the section with an amplitude of 1Pa. For torsion cases, the external load varies across the surface to generate a distributed moment, given by:

$$f(y, z) = 10^7 \begin{bmatrix} -z \\ y \end{bmatrix} \text{ (Pa)} \quad (15)$$

The loading for the circular and square beams can be seen in Figure 5. On the thermal

Figure 5: Loading and boundary conditions for: (a) circular beam, (b) square beam.

side, all boundaries were considered Adiabatic.

The objective of also including bending simulation in this study is to provide a reference for the magnitude of the damping generated by torsion.

All simulations were frequency sweeps from 0 to 200rad/s with an increasing sample rate. The maxima of the damping factor should be in this frequency range because the frequency interval of the maxima is defined by the smallest dimension of the enclosing parallelepiped, [6].

3.3 Results

3.3.1 Circular beam

Starting with the circular beam, results show that, as expected, the torsion does not generate thermoelastic damping, Figure 7.

Figure 6: Hysteretic damping factor for the circular beam: (a) log-lin plot, (b) log-log plot (without torsion).

Because torsion in the circular beam does not generate volume changes, there are no temperature variations and, consequently, no thermoelastic damping. Equation 1 states that, in the absence of external heat flows, only material traction/compression generates temperature variation and, from Equation 4, Entropy loss. Torsion of circular members only generates shear deformations.

3.3.2 Square beam

Moving to the square cross-section beam, the results are now different, Figure 7a. As seen in Figure 7a, the torsion generates damping. Since torsion of non-circular elements creates warping of the cross-section, some areas are under axial deformation and, as such, generate temperature variations, Figure 7b. However, in this case, when comparing with the damping generated by bending, torsional damping is much smaller, in conformity to what was reported by [24].

Figure 7: (a) Hysteretic damping factor for the square beam under bending and torsion, (b) Temperature variation at the cross-section for torsion.

3.3.3 Plate

When studying the effect of torsion in a plate, the results are more pronounced, Figure 8.

Figure 8: Hysteretic damping factor for the plate under bending and torsion.

For plates under torsion, the thermoelastic damping, because it is only one order of magnitude smaller than the one generated by bending, cannot be dismissed as in the previous cases. Due to the very different aspect ratio of the cross-section of the plate, the warping generated by torsion is much higher than in the square beam, and, consequently, the temperature variations are much higher across the cross-section, Figure 9.

Figure 9: Temperature variation for a plate under torsion: (a) at the cross-section, (b) across the plate.

3.3.4 I-beam

While I-beams are not common in the micro-scale, however, due to their cross-section, they make interesting cases to study, Figure 10.

Figure 10: Hysteretic damping factor for the I-beam under bending and torsion.

From Figure 10, it can be seen that the effect of damping in torsion is even more evident in this I-beam than it was in the plate. In this case, the torsion-damping factor is higher in higher frequencies than the one generated by bending. It can be seen in the bending damping (studied in more detail in, [4] and [6]) damping in torsion also has two maxima, showing an overall “mode” of damping in lower frequencies and a more local “mode” of damping, as it can be seen in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Temperature variation at the cross-section for an I-beam under torsion: (a) for a frequency of 0.11rad/s, (b) for a frequency of 20rad/s.

3.3.5 Overall analysis

When comparing all damping factors for all geometries, Figure 12, it can be seen that in bending, the behavior of the damping factor with frequency is essentially the same (except the dual mode of the I-beam), both in magnitude and location of the maximum in frequency. This is justified by all geometries having a more or less similar behavior under bending and the proportions being also identical to each other, which is one of the most important defining factors in thermoelastic damping (more than the actual dimensions that affect only the frequency of the maxima) [4, 6].

Figure 12: Damping factors: (a) for bending, (b) for torsion.

When analyzing the behavior of damping when under torsion, there are notable differ-

ences, especially in magnitude, where the more complex cross-sections with higher aspect ratios have generally higher damping magnitudes, which means that higher warping is the defining factor in thermoelastic damping in torsion.

4 Conclusions

This study primarily aimed to investigate the damping behavior of the thermoelastic effect under torsional loads. The results obtained from simulations using harmonic Finite Element Analysis reveal the following:

- While the behavior of damping under being largely depends on the proportions of the geometries (length versus cross-section dimension), under torsion, convex, and more complex cross-sections have higher damping factors due to high warping.
- Torsional thermoelastic damping in circular and square beams can be safely ignored when also in the presence of bending deformation, but in plates and I-beams, it cannot.
- in higher frequency torsion deformations in I-beam, the torsional damping can be higher than the one created by bending.

This study prompts several questions for future research. Foremost is the imperative to experimentally validate the obtained results under controlled conditions. The model developed for this study can assist in designing the experiment and selecting suitable sensors and actuators. Another question to be explored in future work is the increase in resonant frequencies due to the absence of “thermal inertia” in the heat equation. The speed of the hypothetical thermal wave (or “second sound”, as termed by some authors) should be studied for the materials used in this investigation to refine and update the thermoelastic model.

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